

THE ROLE OF TALENT MANAGEMENT IN MEDIATING THE EFFECTS OF WORK LIFE BALANCE POLICY AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN PT. PERKEBUNAN IV NORTH SUMATRA

FAJAR REZEKI ANANDA¹, SYAIFUDDIN² and YUSNIAR LUBIS³

¹Management Program, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia.
Email: fajarezekiananda@gmail.com

² Professor of Doctor of Management, University of Prima Indonesia, Medan Indonesia.

³ Professor of Doctoral Program in Agricultural Sciences, University of Medan Area, North Sumatra Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

The agricultural sector is an unusual sector in low opinion because this sector is one of the economic veins of a country that depends on agriculture, both in the short and long term (Y.W. Wartaya Winangun). Agriculture has a substantial nature in terms of development because it can act as a fulfillment of food needs, a provider of raw materials for industry, a contributor to foreign exchange, and a provider of employment (Y.W. Wartaya Winangun). To produce maximum production in plantations, it is necessary to pay attention to employee performance. Based on these things, the researchers want to determine and examine the role of talent management in mediating the effects of work life balance policy and knowledge transfer on employee performance in PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV-North Sumatra. The approach used in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). A total of 104 employees of PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV were selected to be the population and sample for this study. Data collection is using a questionnaire as a way for researchers to obtain research data. The results of this study indicate that: work life balance policy directly has a significant effect on employee performance, knowledge transfer directly affects employee performance, talent management directly has a significant effect on employee performance, and lastly, talent management indirectly has a significant effect in mediating the effects of work life balance policy and knowledge transfer on employee performance.

Keywords: Talent management, work life balance policy, knowledge transfer, employee performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The existence of State-Owned Enterprises (SOE) in the Indonesian economy serves to accommodate workers, because in general SOE is a labor-intensive specialty in plantation SOEs, thus opening up vast job opportunities for the people of Indonesia, as a foreign exchange earner, and assisting development of small business units and cooperatives. Thus, the role played by SOE in the Indonesian economy is very supportive of Indonesia's development.

Bureaucratic reform in SOEs in Indonesia has now become the main task, especially the SOE minister (Meirinawati, 2021). Mental reform at every level of management requires everyone to be adaptive, loyal, collaborative, trustworthy, harmonious and competent, which are the core values that employees of SOEs must possess (Pratomo, 2021). This is one way so that SOEs can actively participate in building and contribute to the growth and development of the country through taxes. For this reason, it is expected that all employees can work and contribute every time in their work to provide maximum employee performance. This is in accordance with the

opinions of experts, among others, Mangkunegara (2016: 9) who argues that employee performance is the result of one's work in quality and quantity that has been achieved by employees in carrying out tasks according to the allocated responsibilities. This goal is proclaimed so that SOEs become one of the cornerstones to contribute to the Indonesian State Budget. This expected core value certainly makes every employee work according to their duties and functions. Good governance in SOEs can only be achieved by improving employee performance (Dirkareshza, 2022). This means that what is expected is that every employee is required to have maximum performance and can work well mentally and morally, where every employee who works in SOEs must have a sense of responsibility for the progress or decline of the company.

In working in teams like SOEs, according to the principle of knowledge transfer, one must provide experience and lessons to others, namely from senior employees to junior ones so that knowledge can be passed on to our friends or subordinates. With this transfer of knowledge, it is hoped that it will support the company's progress and in the end the company can achieve its goals in accordance with its Vision and Mission.

This is in accordance with the opinion According to Subagyo (2007) that knowledge sharing is one of the methods or steps in knowledge management that is used to provide opportunities for members of a group, organization, agency, or company to share knowledge, techniques, experiences, and ideas to the other members. According to Pasaribu (2009), knowledge sharing is a culture of social interaction, including the exchange of knowledge between employees, experiences, and skills through entire departments or organizations. This creates the general premise that there is a need for cooperation. Work-life balance must be maintained because if there is no balance between work and rest, it will cause boredom at work. Therefore, the work we are doing must be balanced with our circumstances, where between career and ambition must be balanced.

This is in accordance with the opinion of According to Singh and Khanna (2011) that work-life balance is a broad concept that involves setting the right priorities between work (career and ambition) on the one hand and life (happiness, leisure, family and spiritual development). On the other hand, according to Frame and Hartog (2003:4), work-life balance means that employees can freely use flexible working hours to balance their work or activities with other commitments such as family, hobbies, arts, studies, and not just focus on their work.

In order for the work to be always up to date, the knowledge gained either from the results of our education or from the results of experience in the field must be adjusted to the talents of the employees so that the work is always enjoyable and can be completed quickly. In order for this talent in the organization to be effective, it must be adjusted to the realization of the employee's self-development. This is in line with the opinion of Rampersad (2006:234) that: "Talent management is a way of managing talent in the organization effectively, planning and developing succession in the company, realizing the maximum self-development of employees, and optimal utilization of talent". That's why the urgency of this research is very important, where predictive models or formulas and leading indicators are found in predicting employee performance models with the SEM approach.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS TEST

1. Talent Management

According to Pella (2011), talent management is a process to ensure the company's ability to find key positions for future leaders and positions that support the company's core competencies (unique skills and high strategic value). There are at least several aspects in talent management, namely aspects of identification, development, retention and placement of the right people (Knez & Ruse in Berger & Berger (2004))

Identification of the optimal talent portfolio needs to be carried out by taking into account the impact of investment on the company's ability to achieve strategic and operational targets that match or exceed expectations. This process must be integrated with the regular process of human resource management. The talent management process is designed to ensure that a business develops its competitive advantage through optimal utilization of a small group of individuals in key leadership positions. The definition above states that talent management is basically a combination of initiatives taken by a company to create business excellence by optimizing its talented employees. The key is in the process of identifying, developing, and retaining talented employees to be able to continue to create business advantages for the company. According to previous studies there is a significant relationship between talent management and performance (Cheese et al., 2007; Collings et al., 2019; Hongal & Kinange, 2020; Vural et al., 2012), and also there is a relationship between talent management and leadership (Fadillah, 2018; Goestjahjanti et al., 2020; Hudayah et al., 2021; Nugraha, 2019; Sharma & Bhatnagar, 2009)

2. Work Life Balance

Several experts, among others, Clark in Fapohunda (2014), argue that work life balance has good content at work and also outside of work with minimal conflict (Clark in Fapohunda, 2014). Other authors state that work life balance is how a person seeks balance as well as comfort at work and outside of work. Parkes and Langford (2008) define work life balance as an individual who is able to commit to work and family, and is also responsible for non-work activities. In aligning these two things, a balance is needed, because many employees have difficulty in managing their own work activities and health. This is closely related to the area of human resources where this balance plays an important role in the smooth work and success of employees (Saleem & Abbasi, 2015). Schermerhorn (2005) suggests that work-life balance is a person's ability to balance the demands of work with personal and family needs.

An individual is required to be able to balance his role well even though he has demanding duties and responsibilities in two roles within the organization and outside the organization. According to Greenhaus, et al (2002), balance is seen as the absence of conflict. This is very important in an organization as well as in the personal life of an employee, because if both roles within the organization and outside the organization support each other, there will be no conflict between work life and the role of the employee outside the world of work. According to previous studies, there is a significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Performance (Adnan Bataineh, 2019; Johari et al., 2018a, 2018b; H. K. Kim, 2014; Mwangi et al., 2016;

Obiageli et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2016; Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020; Wiradendi Wolor, 2020; Wiradendi Wolor et al.2020b).

3. Knowledge Transfer

Authors (e.g. Allee, 1997) who view knowledge as an object tend to use the term “knowledge transfer”, while other authors who view knowledge as a process use the term “knowledge sharing”. Knowledge sharing has the same meaning as knowledge transfer. Jacobson & Goering (2006) defines knowledge sharing as an exchange of knowledge between two individuals, where one person communicates knowledge and the other assimilates that knowledge. Meanwhile, according to Sudjiwanati (2017), knowledge transfer is a learning process carried out by parties who are considered more experienced to new employees so that it is expected to facilitate and improve the effectiveness of company performance. According to previous studies there is a significant relationship between Knowledge Transfer and Performance (Antoro, 2014; Chalifa & Nugrohoseno, 2014; Sinaga et al., 2020; Yuningsih & Ramadhina, 2022).

4. Theoretical Framework

According to the related literature review and hypothesis development, this study develops a theoretical framework as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Theoretical Framework

5. Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses in this study are as follows:

- H1: Work life balance policy has a significant effect on Talent Management
- H2: Knowledge transfer has a significant effect on Talent Management
- H3: Work life balance policy has a significant effect on Employee Performance
- H4: Knowledge transfer has a significant effect on Employee Performance
- H5: Talent Management has a significant effect on Employee Performance
- H6: Work life balance policy has a significant effect on Employee Performance through Talent Management
- H7: Knowledge transfer has a significant effect on Employee Performance through Talent Management

III. METHODOLOGY

The design of this study is quantitative research. Data obtained from the distribution of questionnaires with a Likert scale. A total of 98 employees in PTP Nusantara IV were chosen to be the population and sample for this research. Furthermore, the data were analyzed using the Structure Equation Model (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS) which aims to perform path analysis. With this method, the analysis is carried out on the direct effect of the work life balance policy variable and the knowledge transfer variable on the talent management mediating variable and on the independent employee performance variable, as well as the indirect effect of the work life balance policy variable and the knowledge transfer variable on employee performance through talent management.

According to (Sholihin & Ratmono, 2013) SEM-PLS can work efficiently with small sample sizes and complex models. In addition, the assumption of data distribution in SEM-PLS is relatively looser than that of CB-SEM. SEM-PLS is a non-parametric approach that can work well even for data that is not normally distributed in an extreme way. Furthermore, the Partial Least Square (PLS) method was carried out in this study in two stages, namely: 1) The first stage is to test the measurement model (Outer Model), which is to test the validity and reliability of the constructs of each indicator. 2) The second stage is to conduct a structural model test (Inner Model) which aims to determine whether or not there is an effect between variables/correlation between the constructs measured in this study.

IV. RESULTS

1. Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

Convergent Validity Test

Figure 2. Results Model

Based on the picture above, all indicators in the model were greater than 0.7. So it can be concluded that it was reliable for the research variable measurement. Then it can be used in the next analysis.

Construct Reliability Test

The results of data processing are as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Construct Reliability and Validity

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average ...
EP	0.921	0.921	0.934	0.586
KT	0.929	0.929	0.940	0.610
MT	0.918	0.919	0.932	0.578
WBP	0.921	0.923	0.934	0.586

Based on Table 1, it was indicated that the average value is more than 0.5. Then the composite reliability value was more than 0.7. So it can be concluded that the indicators on this the study were able to measure well.

2. Measurement Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The results of data processing for the calculation of the coefficient of determination (R-Square) are as shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. R Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
EP	0.960	0.958
MT	0.927	0.925

Based on the results of the calculations in Table 2, it is known that the R Square Adjusted value for the Employee Performance variable is 0.958 or 95.8% while the remaining 4.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Meanwhile, the value of R Square Adjusted for the talent management variable is 0.925 or 92.5%, while the remaining 7.5% is influenced by other variables not included in this study.

Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The value of Q² has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination (R-Square). The value of Q-Square (Q²) is equal to 0 indicating that the model has predictive relevance. On the contrary, if the value of Q² is less than 0, this indicates that the model has less predictive relevance. In other words, if all the values of Q² are high, then the model can be considered more suitable to the data. Calculation of the value of Q² can be done as follows

$$Q_2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2)(1 - R_2^2) \dots (1 - R_n^2)$$

$$Q_2 = 1 - (1 - 0.958)(1 - 0.925)$$

$$Q_2 = 1 - (0.042)(0.075)$$

$$Q_2 = 1 - 0.003$$

$$Q_2 = 0.997$$

From the above calculation it appears that the value of Q² is 0.997. Thus, it can be concluded that all variables in this study, namely Talent Management, Work life balance policy, Knowledge Transfer, and Employee Performance contributed 99.7% of the original data to the existing structural model. Then the remaining 0.3% needs to be developed apart from the variables in this study.

Effect Size (F2)

Effect Size (F2) is to determine the kindness of the model. It is also used to determine whether the predictor variable has a weak, sufficient or strong effect at the structural level.

3. Hypothesis Test

Table 3. Summary of Calculations for Direct Effects by Path Coefficients

	Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-V...	Confidence Intervals	Confidence Intervals Bias C...		
	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
KT -> EP	0.318	0.306	0.093	3.399	0.001
KT -> MT	0.524	0.526	0.100	5.234	0.000
MT -> EP	0.230	0.241	0.085	2.717	0.007
WBP -> EP	0.454	0.453	0.075	6.090	0.000
WBP -> MT	0.459	0.457	0.103	4.442	0.000

Effect of Knowledge Transfer on Employee Performance

Knowledge Transfer directly has a significant effect on Employee Performance. This result can be seen from the significance value of 0.001 which is smaller than 0.05. This research is in line with the results of previous studies which indicated that Knowledge Transfer has a significant effect on Employee Performance (Antoro, 2014; Chalifa & Nugrohoseno, 2014; Sinaga et al., 2020; Yuningsih & Ramadhina, 2022). The results of this study show the findings that the Knowledge Transfer implemented at PTP Nusantara IV is carried out by providing direction to subordinates so that the knowledge gained during working in the field can be carried out or followed by other employees. Because if the knowledge gained is not developed to be effective, this can interfere with or hinder the development of knowledge within the company, because knowledge transfer is a learning process carried out by parties who are considered more experienced to new employees so that it is expected to facilitate and improve the effectiveness of the company's performance. (Sudjiwanati, 2017)

Effect of Knowledge Transfer on Talent Management

The results of data testing show that Knowledge Transfer directly has a significant effect on Talent Management. It is known that the significance value of Knowledge Transfer is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This means that Knowledge Transfer has a significant effect on Talent Management in PTP Nusantara IV. These results are in line with previous studies conducted by Ridha Choirun Nisa Endang Siti Astuti Arik Prasetya (2016) in PT. PLN (Persero) for Distribution of East Java, Surabaya.

Effect of Talent Management on Employee Performance

The results of data analysis conducted indicate that Talent Management directly has a significant effect on employee performance, where it is known that the significance value of

the Talent Management variable is 0.007 which is smaller than 0.05, Where, in this case, it is known that the significance value of the Talent Management variable is 0.007 which is smaller than 0.05, which means that talent management has a significant effect on PTP Nusantara IV. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous studies which state that talent management has a significant effect on employee performance (Niko Satria Rachmadinata & Hani Gita Ayuningtias, 2014) and talent management has a significant positive effect on employee performance (Hanum Aula Rahmawati, 2019).

Effect of Work Life Balance Policy on Employee Performance

The results of the data analysis carried out concluded that the work life balance policy directly had a significant effect on employee performance, because it was known that the significance value of the work life balance policy variable was 0.000 which was smaller than 0.05. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous studies which state that work life balance policy has a significant effect on employee performance (Adnan Bataineh, 2019; Johari et al., 2018a, 2018b; H. K. Kim, 2014; Mwangi et al., 2016; Obiageli et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2016; Tamunomiebi & Oyibo, 2020; Wiradendi Wolor, et al 2020, 2020b).

Effect of Work Life Balance Policy on Talent Management

The results of the data analysis carried out indicate that the work life balance policy directly has a significant effect on Talent Management, because it is known that the significance value of the work life balance policy variable is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. The results of this study indicate that work time balance must be managed or managed by good instincts or talents in order to balance work time where work life balance is a person's ability to balance work demands with personal and family needs (Schermerhorn, 2005).

Table 4. Summary of Calculations for Indirect Effects

	Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-V...	Confidence Intervals	Confidence Intervals Bias C...		
	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
KT -> MT -> EP	0.120	0.128	0.055	2.183	0.030
WBP -> MT -> EP	0.105	0.109	0.044	2.385	0.017

Effect of Knowledge Transfer on Employee Performance through Talent Management

Talent Management indirectly has a significant effect in mediating the effect of Knowledge Transfer on Employee Performance. It is concluded from the significance value of 0.030 which is smaller than 0.05. This research shows that to convey or transfer knowledge, talent is needed because in this case there is a series of processes carried out by companies to identify, develop, retain, and place the right people in the right places (Nisa, R. C., Astuti, E. S., & Prasetya, 2016). This means that the right person must be placed to transfer the knowledge or talent management is needed in the transfer process.

Effect of Work Life Balance Policy on Employee Performance through Talent Management

Talent Management indirectly has a significant effect in mediating work life balance policy on Employee Performance. This can be seen from the significance value of 0.017 which is smaller than 0.05. This research shows that balancing work time cannot be realized solely by looking at what we want to do, but must have a sensitive feeling towards the environment and family. Working continuously without paying attention to the surrounding environment is not good so that talent is needed to manage working time and does not have to wait for instructions from superiors to divide work time, the important thing is that the work is in accordance with the wishes of the company.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions that researchers can make are that: 1) Work life balance policy and Knowledge Transfer directly have a significant effect on Talent Management and Employee Performance, and 2) Talent Management indirectly has a significant effect in mediating the effects of work life balance policy and Knowledge Transfer on Employee Performance.

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